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Designing a Program on Data Science while supporting Faculty Capacity Building in Latin America

A.F. Salazar-Gomez¹

Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Cambridge, MA, USA

A. Bagiati

Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Cambridge, MA, USA

H. Sive

Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Cambridge, MA, USA

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ABSTRACT

With the advent of Internet and the rising amount of data new technologies produce, data scientists are in-demand professionals, increasing the need for state-of-the-art, cross-disciplinary Data Science programs. However, many universities do not yet have adequate personnel to staff such programs or lack the methodologies that facilitate the teaching-learning process. To address this need, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology Abdul Latif Jameel World Education Lab (MIT J-WEL) is collaborating with the Government of Uruguay, by supporting development of a framework to guide a blended graduate program in data science, machine learning and entrepreneurship.

This novel framework integrates physical and digital learning environments. It combines asynchronous online material from the MITx Statistics and Data Science MicroMasters®, accompanied by MITx entrepreneurship courses. In parallel it introduces the core concept of synchronous online mentoring session, complemented by a series of in-person workshops. Finally, concurrent with other program elements, the framework focuses on development of expert Uruguayan faculty who will be able to educate data science professionals in the future.

The program is strongly interdisciplinary and the content for online mentoring sessions and in-person workshops is under development by MIT researchers and staff, with

¹ Corresponding Author
A.F.Salazar-Gomez
salacho@mit.edu

attention to specific audience and local context. Target students for the program are digital native professionals, with 60 learners in the first cohort. The program began in May 2019 and lasts 15 months.

This paper describes this multifaceted framework that is particularly designed to educate a new generation of data scientists while in parallel developing expert faculty capacity in Uruguay.

1 INTRODUCTION

We are living in a world where the boundaries between the digital, physical, and biological spheres are becoming more intertwined day by day. “This technological convergence is increasingly being referred to as the ‘fourth industrial revolution’, and like its predecessors, it promises to transform the ways we live and the environments we live in” [1]. As this revolution already takes place, according to the 2016 World Economic Forum Report (WEFR) on the Future of Jobs [2], Big Data and Machine Learning are considered to be among the most important drivers of change, making the need for advancements in the Data Engineering and Data Science fields critical. Data generation, acquisition, and analysis appear to be at the epicenter of this change and Data Science is already affecting critical development in “healthcare, economic productivity, and security” [3]; and driving changes in work sectors such as Policy Making [3,4], Medicine [5], Commerce [6], Banking [7], and Education [8]. According to the WEFR, in regards to Big Data, “realizing the full potential of technological advances will require having in place the systems and capabilities to make sense of the unprecedented flood of data these innovations will generate” [2].

Moreover, local and global economies, public and private institutions, collective or single users, are generating information that has become a new type of currency in the digital economy: data/currency that is expected to grow exponentially in the future. A report by the IADB (Inter-American Development Bank), suggests that worldwide commercial purchases of data and data-related services are “expected to maintain a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 11.9% through 2020, when revenues will be more than \$210 billion.” [9]. Also, this report reveals that Latin America and the Caribbean will present the fastest growth in data-related purchases with a “five-year CAGR of 16.2% from 2015 to 2020”.

Within the current digital ecosystem, infrastructure to support Big Data needs to be optimally designed and then Big Data can be generated, harvested, tracked, filtered, analysed and consumed. Data engineers have to carefully understand current and rapidly emerging future needs in order to develop the most efficient products to serve different markets, while data scientists have to keep creating and deploying new analytic models to support and promote appropriate decision-making, in order for their customers to be able to best evaluate past practices and to most accurately project future outcomes. However, although very promising work opportunities for data engineers and data scientists have been predicted and discussed for over a decade

now [10], there is already a great shortage of skilled employees ready to lead this change, and although “much has been said about the need for reform in basic education, it is simply not possible to weather the current technological revolution by waiting for the next generation’s workforce to become better prepared.” [2]

Under the current circumstances, universities around the world are already working to rapidly develop this emerging field. However, although a large number of data science and data engineering programs are being developed for both residential and online use, the Latin America region has a deficit in such programs and require faculty that are not only experts in the field, but also in pedagogy innovation and new teaching technologies.

To counter the deficit in a Data Science program suitable for the Latin American region, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology Abdul Latif Jameel World Education Lab (MIT J-WEL) is currently supporting the Government of Uruguay and local universities to develop a blended graduate program across the fields of data science, machine learning and entrepreneurship. The program accepted its first group of students in May 2019, and is offered to professionals with a strong technical background, the desire to explore new entrepreneurial avenues within their companies or outside of them, and the will to become the region’s future leaders in the field of data science. The participant’s median age is 36 years old, one third of them are female; half of the learners are engineers, and a quarter of them are economist. Also, a fifth of the participants are university professors in diverse fields (entrepreneurship, engineering, and economics). The framework, developed to guide program development and implementation has two aspects both designed to expedite and accomplish the intended program goals: educating a new generation of Latin American data scientists and entrepreneurs, while in parallel building faculty capacity and transferring knowledge to the partner universities in Uruguay.

2 THE FRAMEWORK

2.1 Content

Content will be delivered over 4 trimesters and consists of a combination of required and elective courses addressing Data Science and Entrepreneurship. In greater detail, courses will include:

- Four online MITx Statistics and Data Science MicroMasters® courses: Introduction to Probability - The Science of Uncertainty, Data Analysis for Social Scientist, Fundamental of Statistics, and Machine Learning with Python: From Linear Models to Deep Learning. If all courses are accomplished, the learners can take a final proctored exam to obtain the MicroMasters certificate.
- Two online elective MITx entrepreneurship courses (Entrepreneurship 101 and Shaping work of the future).

- Seven different elective online courses taught by Uruguayan universities (Universidad de la República and UTEC), spanning the use of R for data analysis and Machine learning to multiple language learning.
- Three residential workshops addressing
 - Introduction to data science and entrepreneurship.
 - MIT Global Startup Labs PRO (a technology incubator course focused on developing a model for a product or a company using entrepreneurship, machine learning, and data science).
 - A project presentation focused on raising seed funds.

The Micromasters and entrepreneurship courses are pre-existing courses previously developed for a broader audience. Courses developed by the Uruguayan universities are either adapted or newly developed courses, and the workshops are particularly tailored to the program.

2.2 Delivery

This novel framework employs the *blended learning* and *mentoring* learning theories as the main delivery mechanisms, as it combines asynchronous online classes with synchronous online mentoring sessions and complements these with residential workshops that will take place in Uruguay. In all cases content delivery is guided by the MIT motto “*Mens et Manus*”, (“mind and hand” in English), making hands-on learning the driving teaching approach [11]. Furthermore, to support delivery, the framework integrates physical and digital learning environments based on the content covered. In greater detail:

- MicroMasters® and entrepreneurship courses are offered on the edX platform.
- Online elective courses offered by Uruguayan universities use the edX, open.edX and Moodle platforms.
- Residential workshops include hands-on and face-to-face activities in Uruguay, and synchronous video conferences using Adobe connect.
- Synchronous mentoring sessions use Moodle and Adobe connect.
- Live discussion forums, led by faculty from Uruguayan universities, will be available on the Moodle platform.

The different delivery mechanisms are presented in Fig. 1, while Fig. 2 presents integration of the various learning environments in greater detail.

Fig 1. Delivery mechanisms

Fig 2. Learning environments

2.3 Faculty development and knowledge transfer

The driving force for the development of this framework has been the need to train local Uruguayan faculty in innovative blended learning models, adequately incorporating and using technology during instruction. In order to expedite offering this graduate program, while in parallel ensuring appropriate faculty training, program developers from MIT and local universities have particularly designed a Faculty Development Program (FDP) where local faculty will be receiving training on data science as well as on the appropriate didactical methods throughout the program. The same training will be attended by MIT personnel who will serve as mentors to the program. “Learning through teaching” is the main learning theory employed for the faculty development program. However, active participation in classes and mentorship sessions will also introduce them to all appropriate active learning pedagogies suggested by MIT to deliver the data science related content.

The current FDP starts one month before the beginning of the designated courses, as presented in Fig. 3, and continues throughout the life span of three student cohorts. During the first cohort, faculty from Uruguayan universities will be actively enrolled in the MITx MicroMasters® courses, while they will be trained by MIT to support the MIT-led mentoring sessions. During the second cohort, both MIT and UU mentors will share equal responsibilities during mentoring sessions. For the third cohort, the UU mentors will take the leading role during mentoring sessions. Fig. 4 Introduces how the leadership role transitions from MIT to UU mentors across cohorts.

Fig 3. Mentor training process

Fig 4. Leadership role transition for MIT to UU mentors across cohorts

3 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we have presented a novel framework that is designed to accelerate development of an academic program in Data Science by synchronizing launching of the academic program together with the FDP, taking full advantage of this parallel process. Although this framework has been developed with this particular program in mind, it can easily be adapted to supporting other emerging fields.

The inaugural cohort for this program started in May 2019, and attendees represent an international population, mainly stemming from Latin American countries, with diverse professional backgrounds. The Program aspires not only to educate the learners but also to move beyond formal education by promoting formation of a long-lasting community, as well as creation of a knowledge base for the future data scientist of the region, while still fostering MIT engagement with the future scientists of the world. Finally, we are also planning a careful evaluation of teaching, learning, and online mentoring processes as well as the content developed to address the Latin American context, with intent to guide future development both of the academic and faculty development program.

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